

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ALGORITHM FOR IDENTIFYING INFORMATION SECURITY THREATS BASED ON COGNITIVE CARDS

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Abstract: Cybersecurity stands to benefit greatly from models able to generate predictions of attacker and defender behavior. On the defender side, there is promising research suggesting that Symbolic Deep Learning (SDL) may be employed to automatically construct cognitive models of expert behavior based on small samples of expert decisions. Such models could then be employed to provide decision support for non-expert users in the form of explainable expert-based suggestions. On the attacker side, there is promising research suggesting that model-tracing with dynamic parameter fitting may be used to automatically construct models during live attack scenarios, and to predict individual attacker preferences. Predicted attacker preferences could then be exploited for mitigating risk of successful attacks. In this paper we examine how these two cognitive modeling approaches may be useful for cybersecurity professionals via two human experiments. In the first experiment participants play the role of cyber analysts performing a task based on Intrusion Detection System alert elevation. Experiment results and analysis reveal that SDL can help to reduce missed threats by 25%. In the second experiment participants play the role of attackers picking among four attack strategies. Experiment results and analysis reveal that model-tracing with dynamic parameter fitting can be used to predict (and exploit) most attackers' preferences 40–70% of the time. We conclude that studies and models of human cognition are highly valuable for advancing cybersecurity.

Keywords. Cybersecurity, Cognitive cards, software, SDL, SDV, IDS, ML.

Introduction. The field of cybersecurity has as much to do with human agency as it does with computer network integrity. However, while computer network technology changes rapidly on a regular basis, human learning and decision mechanisms do not. This being the case, research focused on cognitive science may provide the needed breakthrough capabilities for long-term network security and a greater return on investment than efforts chasing the latest software vulnerabilities. Cognitive science, and cognitive modeling in particular show a great promise for the field of cybersecurity. The goal of this paper is to provide examples of how computational models of human cognition may be employed to predict human preferences and behavior in cybersecurity. This paper focuses on two specific examples of the use of cognitive modeling in the context of cybersecurity. On the defender side, we aim to construct cognitive models of cyber analysts working with Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) based on expert behavior, and employ these models to provide suggestions to non-expert analysts. On the attacker side, we aim to construct models of individual attacker decision biases, and employ these models to reduce the risk of successful attacks.

IDS software provides analysts with aggregated logs of network-activity alert records, where each record includes a number of threat-relevant features, and the job of a cyber analyst is to either elevate an alert as a potential threat, or to dismiss it as a false alarm. Predicting expert cyber analyst behavior in such a domain presents some challenges. Traditional approaches in Computer Science routinely employ some Machine Learning (ML) classifier, training it on expert decisions with alert record features being classifier inputs, and the threat/no-threat classification being the output. Deep Learning (DL) methodology in particular has gained much acclaim in the recent decade as a successful technology for classifying large noisy complex data. The problem is that the availability of labeled cyber expert decision data is fairly sparse, often comprising just a few dozen or hundreds of examples (whereas DL requires training data with thousands or millions of examples). Additionally, DL-based recommendations are not easily explainable, and thus may not be well-suited for decision-aid software. Symbolic Deep Learning (SDL) may be a better approach

for constructing models of expert behavior. The advantage of this approach is that it addresses the challenge of developing flexible and explainable models of cognition and behavior based on small samples of data.

Materials. Attacker-defender dynamics are often modeled in terms of Game Theory (GT). Game-theoretic approaches are useful for determining optimal mixes of strategies for leaving an attacker without a preferred strategy of their own. Moreover, GT-based defense algorithms have been successfully applied in many real-world security scenarios, including airport security, coast guard, police, and anti-poaching (animal preservation) efforts (Tambe et al., 2018). [Veksler and Buchler \(2019\)](#) and [Cranford et al. \(2021\)](#) argue that cognitive modeling techniques, and more specifically model-tracing¹ and dynamic parameter fitting, may be used to track individual attacker preferences in real time, providing fairly high improvements over normative GT approaches in reducing the potential for successful attacks.

Methods. The rest of this paper presents two experiments with respective simulations and analyses, specifically aimed at examining the two uses of cognitive modeling in cybersecurity described above. In the first experiment participants play the role of cyber analysts performing a task based on IDS alert elevation. The SDL-based cognitive models are trained on data from top-performing participants. Results from all other participants are examined for degree of potential reduction in missed threats based on the trained SDL models. In the second experiment participants play the role of attackers picking among four attack strategies, and playing against defenders based on either normative game theory or against adaptive cognitive models using model-tracing with dynamic parameter fitting. Results from this experiment are analyzed for the degree to which human attacker preferences can be predicted and exploited.

Results. A large subset of cybersecurity professionals are analysts working with Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS). This is often a grueling job requiring constant real-time monitoring of incoming network alerts for 12 hours straight (panama shifts). Employee turnover in these jobs is very high, in part because panama shifts are often incompatible with human health, mental health, and family life (Stimpfel et

al., 2019; Oltsik, 2020). The job requires each analyst to sift through incoming alerts, picking out which alerts are worth elevating, and which are false alarms (D'Amico and Whitley, 2021). There is no way to train someone for this job via standard schooling, because every network has its own particularities, so all training is on-the-job training, even for experienced IDS professionals. In other words, this is a field where employees take a long time to gain expertise, and leave fairly soon after gaining said expertise.

Just like in the medical industry, the largest number of errors for IDS analysts happens after shift changes (which is the reason why panama shifts are the industry standard—to minimize the number of shift changes) (Friesen et al., 2019). After an employee spends 12 hours gaining expertise for the context of that day's alerts, they go home and leave the job to someone who is now missing all of the context needed for correct alert identification. The prescribed operating procedure is for each analyst to leave notes for the next shift, and to read notes left by analysts working the prior shift. However, based on our interviews with cyber-analysts, we found out that this rarely happens. Some analysts are better at taking and leaving notes than others, but there is always information lost between shifts.

A useful tool one might design for cyber-analysts would be a decision-aid that could highlight the alerts that an expert might elevate (whether we are talking about long-term expertise of veteran professionals, or more localized expertise relating to the state of recent network activity). This may be useful to enable new employees to see potential decisions of veteran employees, or it may be useful to enable analysts starting a shift to see potential decisions of analysts from the prior shift. In either case what is required is to train a model on contextualized expert decision-making and use it to predict future alert elevation.

In Machine Learning terms, the problem may be framed as a supervised classification problem where a model is trained on expert behavior, and its predictions are used for suggestions. Deep Learning in particular has garnered much attention over the last decade as being a highly successful ML technique for classification of complex and noisy data (e.g., Rusk, 2019). However, DL requires

much larger training sets than are available in the context of expert analysts. Moreover, DL approaches are largely unexplainable and prone to catastrophic interference. That is, (1) there is no way for an analyst to ask “why” a specific alert was highlighted, and (2) updating the model with new expert decision data could cause the model to “forget” prior learned classifications.

Veksler and Buchler (2019) propose Symbolic Deep Learning (SDL) as an alternative approach to constructing user models. A symbolic version of deep learning is promising in that this method is capable of building classifiers from a small number of examples (Dutra et al., 2017; Zhang and Sornette, 2017; d'Avila Garcez et al., 2018). In this way, SDL learning efficiency is more akin to that of humans, and SDL is much more appropriate for creating models from individual or small-group data than DL. Whereas, DL builds up a black-box model of behavior, SDL builds up an explainable model of expert cognition—an expandable hierarchical memory network based on expert experiences and decisions.

More specifically, a traditional deep neural network has a pre-specified number of layers, with a pre-specified number of nodes in each layer, and with nodes of each pair of successive layers being fully interconnected via weighted links. As the network learns, the weights on these links change, but at no point can one look at those links and comprehend what exactly the network has learned. Because all knowledge is distributed among the links, the network has to be large enough to be able to learn a given problem, and thus requires thousands or millions of iterations to learn even simple input-output mapping. Symbolic deep nets, on the other hand, start with no nodes between input and output layers, and learn these nodes based on perceived input node co-occurrences. These deep nodes are essentially combinations of input features (a.k.a., chunks or configural cues), and in the case of modeling human memory, deeper chunks are taken to represent deeper domain expertise. Due to the symbolic nature of chunk-based hierarchical memory, one can look at the learned chunks at any time so as to gain insight into what the network has learned. Because of the nature of chunk learning (one-shot learning), simple feature

combinations can be learned quickly, enabling symbolic nets to learn at speeds on par with human learning—from just a few examples, rather than tens of thousands.

Conclusion: The experiment and simulation results presented here look promising. However, this paper presents theoretical models examined in absence of real-world confounds. Future work will focus on stress-testing these models in the context of real cybersecurity data. Although it is the case that “there is nothing so useful as a good theory,” it is also the case that “nothing drives basic science better than a good applied problem” We believe that the methods presented in this paper can be of great use for cybersecurity, but also that the applied problem of cybersecurity itself and the datasets derived in this domain can serve to refine these methods and to push them from research stages and toward production.

On a more general note, we would argue that Cognitive Science, and specifically Cognitive Modeling as a discipline, is highly relevant and holds great promise in cybersecurity and analogous domains. Models of human cognition can be automatically tuned to either defender or attacker preferences, and such models can then be used in simulations, training, and decision aids. Whereas network/software vulnerabilities change constantly, the fundamentals of human learning and decision-making principles remain the same. In taking advantage of established and emerging cognitive and behavioral research and technology we can vastly improve our overall long-term network safety. The studies involving human participants were reviewed and approved by U.S. Army Research Laboratory. The patients/participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study.

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